

Research article

BUILDING RESILIENCE THROUGH LOCAL AND INTERNATIONAL PARTNERSHIPS, NIGERIA EXPERIENCES

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Abstract: Current human development pathways tend to increase disaster impacts, and many disaster impacts are likely to increase due to anthropogenic activities that catalyse epidemiological virus mutation impact series, global warming, and climate change. No specific federal agency is exclusively responsible for disaster management as all the required scientific skills and fiscal resources are not in situ. It is also a fact that global pandemic like COVID-19 has local implications, and that local management of the disease has international implications, as revealed in this study. The study actually examined Nigeria's experience in building national resilience through local and international coalition amidst disaster diplomacy among strong nations. The study also assessed the country's National Emergency Management Agency's programmes and other international donor agencies like UNDP, EU and NGOs' pilot projects surveys. It is revealed that the idea of the global village is fully exemplified as COVID-19 impacts is every one's business and that Nigeria, as a major beacon in Sub-Sahara countries, is a laboratory for disaster diplomacy testing in understanding how donor competition shapes recipients' policy and support. Therefore, a symbiosis relationship among nations and agencies is recommended to enhance the DRR issue.

Keywords: COVID-19, Coronavirus, DRR, Disaster Diplomacy, Disaster Resilience, Foreign Aids, Disaster vulnerability, Global pandemic, Inclusive policy, International coalition, Political Synergy, Sub-Sahara countries.

1. Introduction

That disasters will continue to occur is as certain as saying the sun will rise or set especially with the new discoveries in coronavirus mutations, but actions that move a nation, region or community from reactive to a more proactive activity that enhance resilience will reduce

many of the broad societal and economic burdens that disasters often cause. The pattern and levels of cities development shapes disaster risk, and disaster risk also shapes development possibilities since human life itself is risk as they are causers of risk and recipients of risk It has been generally asserted that no nation or community is immune from disasters or disaster-related losses. Challenging issues that are anthropogenic related like; Earthquake, Tsunami, Wildfire, Drought, Flooding, Heat wave, Epidemic outbreaks, and Terrorism can all lead to large-scale consequences for the nation and its communities. Communities and the nation thus face difficult fiscal, social, cultural, and environmental choices about the best ways to ensure basic security and quality of life against hazards, deliberate attacks, and disasters. Beyond the unquantifiable costs of injury and loss of life from disasters, statistics for 2011 alone indicate economic damages from natural disasters in the United States exceeded \$55 billion, with 14 events costing more than a billion dollars in damages each, (NRC, 2012).

One way to reduce the impacts of disasters on the nation and its communities is to invest in enhancing resilience, (UNDP, 2004). Resilience by way of defined is the ability to prepare and plan for, absorb, recover from, and more successfully adapt to adverse events. Enhanced resilience allows better anticipation of disasters and better planning to reduce disaster losses—rather than waiting for an event to occur and paying for it afterward. Although, building the culture and practice of disaster resilience is not inexpensive or complex. Decisions about how and when to invest in increasing resilience involve short- and long-term planning and investments of time and resources prior to an event. Although the resilience of individuals and communities may be readily recognized after a disaster, resilience is currently rarely acknowledged before a disaster takes place, making the “payoff” for resilience investments challenging for individuals, communities, the private sector, and all levels of government to demonstrate. An important responsibility for increasing national resilience lies with residents and their communities. Input, guidance, and commitment from all levels of government and from the private sector, academia, and community-based and nongovernmental organizations are needed throughout the entire process of building more resilient communities.

In fulfilment of the adage that says ‘A friend in need, is a friend in deed’ create a test bed for international donor competition in countries like Nigeria as a major market dumping site for global economic powers like US and China. For instance, according to Chung et al (2020) making reference to Wilson Center, China gave \$129,966,634.2 more than the U.S. (China’s total assistance of \$297,895,104.4 vs. U.S.’s assistance of \$167,928,470.2) in total aid more to Latin American nations during the COVID-19 pandemic in March-August 2020 This paper, therefore, examine the pattern of foreign aids to Nigeria before and during the pandemic as a way of wooing the country and the same time strengthening national resilient while preventing spill-over effects of disaster mismanagement globally.

2. Review of literature

In building resilience to disasters, there is the need to fully understand, manage, and disseminate foundation on disaster risks reduction. The leadership should establish a national “culture of resilience,” a full and clear commitment to disaster resilience by the federal government is essential (NAP, 2012). Risk management therefore is a continuous process that identifies the hazard(s) facing a community, assesses the risk from these hazards, develops and implements risk management strategies, re-evaluates and reviews these strategies and policies. Risk management strategies requires regular re-evaluation in the context of new data and best practices on the hazards and risk facing a community, and changes in the socioeconomic and demographic characteristics of a community, as well as the community’s

goals. Although some residual risk will always be present, risk management strategies can help build capacity for communities to become more resilient to disasters.

Historical patterns of disaster losses provide some sense of the magnitude of the need to become more disaster resilient. The geographic patterns of disaster losses—e.g., human fatalities, property losses, and crop losses—illustrate where the impacts are the greatest, what challenges exist in responding to and recovering from disasters, and what factors drive exposure and vulnerability to hazards and disasters. Although, most countries lack a national repository for all hazard and loss data, causes the compromising the ability of communities to make informed decisions about where and how to prioritize their resilience investments.

International collaborations on disaster management and resilience building have been in the front burner of UN bodies and NGOs. Most developing countries depend on developed countries for aids when it comes to disaster event. Although from the definition of disaster, an event is termed disaster when their occurrences overwhelm the affected community or nation, and so if nations depend on others for intervention is note out of place. In comparison, a pandemic is defined as an event where there is a sudden increase in cases that spread across several countries and affects a large number of people” (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2020). While the WHO specified that to reach pandemic status, a disease must have caused significant outbreaks in at least two countries within a region, and one country outside of the region.

Foreign aids, however, have a lot of connotation as observed by Chung et al (2020), and Ferry and Cleo (2020). They both see disaster assistance having political consequences for donors, recipients, and the relationship between the two. The politics of emergency health assistance follow many of the same patterns as general humanitarian disaster aid. Chung et al (2020) referred to Morgenthau (1962) to have described aid as little more than a bribe, and that recent studies show that the instrumental benefits derived from providing aid far exceed its humanitarian value. This is very obvious where donor governments use aid as a foreign policy instrument to influence recipient states’ policy choices, (Spaniel 2020). Studies on aid in the context of the UN politics have revealed “vote-buying” patterns to foreign aid as a motivated tool to reward or induce recipient countries.

2.1. International Conventions on DRR

Disaster risk and resilience seem not to receive sufficient emphasis in the original Millennium Development Goal agenda, even though there is a great relationship between disasters and development. Although it is universally accepted that disasters do erode and destroy development gains, there is limited recognition of the role that different approaches to development play in creating or increasing vulnerability. Building the Resilience of Nations and Communities to Disasters was therefore adopted at the World Conference on Disaster Reduction in Kobe, Hyogo, Japan in 2005.

The Framework (The Hyogo Framework for Action 2005-2015) serves as the guiding instrument for international cooperation, disaster risk reduction and resilience building. The multi-stakeholder and multi-sector nature of the Hyogo Framework for Action provides guidance on how disaster risk reduction contributes to sustainable development.

Following on the outcome of the 2010 High-level Plenary Meeting of the General Assembly on the Millennium Development Goals, the United Nations Secretary-General established the UN System Task Team in September 2011 to support UN system-wide preparations for the post-2015 UN development agenda, in consultation with all stakeholders. From the ‘preparedness saves lives’ approach came the insight that economics played a significant

role and a recognition that a longer-term approach was required to reduce disaster risk and build resilience.

The Hyogo Framework for Action (HFA) on disaster – focused on disaster losses and the Sendai Framework concentrates on disaster risk reduction that charts the global course on DRR matters over the next 15 years, (Sendai Framework 2015-2030). One of the framework's core concerns is that more dedicated action needs to be focused on tackling underlying disaster risk drivers and strengthening good governance in DRR strategies at all levels and across sectors and institutions. Also, because disasters such as floods know no borders, effective response requires transboundary or regional coordination and cooperation, the UNECE supports the implementation the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 (SF-DRR), was adopted at the Third UN World Conference in Sendai, Japan, on March 18, 2015

As a follow up, the national or community targets are recognized as best practice for effective implementation, while some specific examples of national level goals or indicators can be seen in Bangladesh (Sixth Five-Year Plan 2011-15), Mozambique (Five Year Government Plan 2010-14 and Master Plan for Disaster Prevention and Mitigation 2006), Peru (State Policy 32) and Philippines (Philippine Development Plan 2010-14). In the same vein, the Tunisia African/Arab platform of 2018 focused on disaster risk Informed and inclusive sustainable development that is geared toward actualizing the Sendai Framework in Africa.

2.2 Inclusiveness in building national Resilience

Disaster resilience has been defined from different perspectives depending on the definers background, as a process (Norris et al., 2008; Sherrieb et al., 2010), as an outcome (Kahan et al., 2009), or both (Cutter et al., 2008), and as a term that can embrace inputs from engineering and the physical, social, and economic sciences (Colten et al., 2008). According to UNISDR (2011), it is the ability to prepare and plan for, absorb, recover from, or more successfully adapt to actual or potential adverse events. A natural or technological hazard can have different short or long-term impacts on various groups within society. For instance, a person's gender, age, physical abilities, ethnicity and sexuality, for instance, can lead to a higher risk of death or injury, longer recovery times, or greater risk of mental or physical trauma. Equally, different groups may bring unique skills, resources and knowledge to reduce risk and overcome the aftermath of a disaster, (Cutter et al, 2010). The strengths and challenges of each group should be recognized at an early stage of preparing the assessment. In building a formidable community resilient along the Sendai Framework, some universal steps that aid local communities in making progress in their resilience include the following:

- I) Engaging the whole community in disaster policymaking and planning;
- II) Linking public and private infrastructure performance and interests to resilience goals;
- III) Improving public and private infrastructure and essential services (such as health and education);
- IV) Communicating risks, connecting community networks, and promoting a culture of resilience;
- V) Organizing communities, neighborhoods, and families to prepare for disasters;
- VI) Adopting sound land-use planning practices; and
- VII) Adopting and enforcing building codes and standards appropriate to existing hazards.

While the characteristics of a resilient nation in the year 2030 according to NAS (2012) is as follows:

I) Every individual and community in the nation has access to the risk and vulnerability information they need to make their communities more resilient.

II) All levels of government, communities, and the private sector have designed resilience strategies and operation plans based on this information.

III) Proactive investments and policy decisions have reduced loss of lives, costs, and socio-economic impacts of future disasters.

IV) Community coalitions are widely organized, recognized, and supported to provide essential services before and after disasters occur.

V) Recovery after disasters is rapid and the per capita federal cost of responding to disasters has been declining for a decade.

VI) Nationwide, the public is universally safer, healthier, and better educated.

2.3 Impacts of exclusion in building national resilience

Exclusion generally erodes community resilience and the current physical planning approaches tend to be reinforcing spatial segregation and creating spaces of exclusion. Insecure tenure impedes infrastructure and services, thus further reinforcing marginality and poverty. Eviction and tenure insecurity destroys social networks and capital and encourages corruption and criminal networks. Territorialisation and isolation of communities creates tensions, especially in cities of diversity, less interaction of people in urban society negatively affects a shared sense of urban citizenship. For many, life is characterised by tenuous connections –to jobs, land, housing and even the ‘right’ to stay in the city. There is a cost for individuals, households and cities in marginalisation and exclusion which include Illegal housing (slums, informal settlements) are rarely included in urban planning and governance which often provide impediments to physical planning.

3. Nature of disaster in Nigeria

Nationwide natural disaster is not very prevalent in Nigeria comparatively not until the 2012 flood episode. Present, the most devastating prevalent disaster in the country is the seasonal flood and insurgences. Flash floods are common occurrences in Nigeria during the rainy season (May-October), but the flood events of the year 2012 have been described as the worst in over 40 years; and this is attributed to the Ladgo Dam water release Flood and the Niger River Flood. The release of waters from Ladgo dam in Cameroon into the Benue River flood plain, coupled with the effect of global warming were largely responsible for the 2012 flooding in Nigeria. These events forces most of the country’s rivers to overflow their banks thereby submerging series of urban and rural settlements including their farm lands. The significance of the year 2012 flood disasters in Nigeria lies in the fact that they were unprecedented in the past forty years as revealed in figure. 1. However, the ability to measure vulnerability is increasingly being seen as a key step towards effective risk reduction and promotion of disaster resilience culture (Birkmann, 2006).

Figure 1. 2012 flood episode in Nigeria.

The insurgencies perpetrated by the Islamic sect ‘Boko-haram’ that was incubated in Borno State around 2010 has become a nightmare in the country and eating deep into the economy of the nation with continuous increase in the number of Internally Displaced persons (IDP) camps all over the country. The impact of flash floods and insurgencies is wide spread and devastating across the country as displayed in Fig 2.

Figure2. Spatial distribution of floods and insurgencies in Nigeria.

Strong governance at all levels is a key element of resilience and it includes the making of consistent and complementary local, state, and federal policies. Although resilience at its core has to be carried forward by communities, communities do not exist under a single authority in Nigeria, but rather function under a mix of policies and practices implemented and enforced by different levels of government. Policies that make the nation more resilient are important in every aspect of Nigerian life and economy, (Rose, A. 2009, 2010) , and not just during times of stress or trauma. A key role of policies designed to improve national resilience is to take the long-term view of community resilience and to help avoid short-term expediencies that can diminish resilience.

Certain policies of the legislative bodies, including Presidential Executive Directives with political undertone and policies initiated by federal agencies can and do function to help strengthen resilience. Many of the critical policies and actions required for improved national resilience are also enacted and implemented at the state and local levels, (CARRI, 2011). Policies at all levels of governance do exist to enhance resilience; however, some government policies and practices can also have unintended consequences that negatively affect resilience.

4.1 Disaster Management in Nigeria

For the first time in 1976, the Federal Government of Nigeria established the National Emergency Relief Agency (NERA) to coordinate national disaster response activities that is purely a relief outfit, focussing only on post disaster management. The continuous increase in deaths from natural and man-made disasters makes mitigation and prevention of disasters an urgent priority. Consequently in 1999, the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) was established in place of NERA to manage disasters in the country holistically. The operational system of the agency is as revealed in figure 3 across the country. In an effort to fulfil its mandate, the agency facilitated the establishment of the National Platform for DRR to advocate and coordinate national level DRR and provide policy direction on DRR priority issues and action areas through a coordinated and participatory process.

The National Disaster Management Framework (NDMF) provides a mechanism that serves as a regulatory guideline for effective and efficient disaster management in Nigeria. Some of the framework’s objectives are:

- a) Establish functional disaster management institutions at all levels of governance to prepare for, prevent, mitigate, respond to and recover from disaster events in Nigeria.
- b) Develop capacity of relevant institutions and stakeholders for effective and efficient disaster management in Nigeria.

Figure 3. Horizontal and Vertical Coordination of Disaster Management in Nigeria

The thematic area mandates the establishment of Disaster Management structures at all levels of governance (federal, states and local) in Nigeria. It centres on the principles of shared responsibility and the need to ensure proper integration and collaboration among stakeholders. There is the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) at the Federal level, State Emergency Management Agency (SEMA) at the state level, and Local Emergency Management Authority (LEMA) at the local government level. This to a large extent shall strengthen the capabilities of Federal, State and Local Governments to reduce the likelihood and severity of disasters. At the state level, there are state operations offices of NEMA across the 36 states and Abuja that report directly to the national headquarter in addition to the regional warehouses for emergency relief in all the geopolitical zones of the country. For the human capacity development, Apart from the international trainees that the officer are

exposed to, NEMA also established six training centers in each of the geopolitical zones to carryout human capacity development at postgraduate level and research activities in DRR that has direct bearing on the local communities within some selected Universities across the country.

4.2 International Collaborating bodies

The Federal government of Nigeria has been and will continue to collaborate with international bodies and government on DRR for effective governance. For example, the federal government and the European Commission entered into cooperation for the period 2014-2020 for a National Indicative Programme in favour of the Federal Republic of Nigeria in tune of €512 million. The A-allocation of the programme is destined to cover macroeconomic support, sectoral policies, programmes and projects, while the B-allocation is destined to cover unforeseen needs such as humanitarian, emergency and post emergency assistance, where such support cannot be financed from the EU budget

Haas and Prabin (2020) however emphasis the fact that there is a dearth of empirical evidence on how disasters impact international collaboration especially in peacekeepers' ability to contain local-level violence even though there is an overwhelming consensus on the ability of international collaborating bodies in sustainable development and peacekeepers to prevent civil war recurrence. The resent COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted negatively on project implementation in recipient countries. For instance, An African Union Peacekeeping Mission in Somalia AMISOM report states that the pandemic had resulted in \ reduced information/intelligence flow on Al-Shabaab due to limited interaction of the troops with the local communities and individual Somali nationals" (AMISOM, 2020).

4.2.1 The GFDRR - the Global Facility for Disaster Reduction and Recovery (GFDRR) that is supported by 37 countries and 11 international organizations and hosted at the World Bank, is a global partnership established in 2006 to support developing countries to understand, manage, and ultimately reduce their risk from natural hazards and climate change; has been granting series of award on environmental issue since 2007 in Nigeria. Some of those specific programmes are listed below:

I) Enhancing Country Capacity to Develop, Implement and Trigger a CERC in an Emergency \$271,136 07/2017 - 11/2017

II) Improving Resilience and Resilience Impact of National Land and Geospatial Systems \$500,000 09/2017 - 07/2019

III) Disaster risk management in Africa: operational support, capacity development. \$800,000 02/2018 - 02/2020

IV) Strengthening Disaster Risk Management Capacity in Ibadan, Nigeria. \$200,000 03/2018 - 09/2019

V) World Reconstruction Conference 3 - Knowledge and Lessons Learned from ACP Countries. \$344,465 03/2017 - 04/2018

VI) Just-in-Time Capacity Building and Advice for Climate Resilience. \$3,100,000 01/2015 - 12/2018

VII) City Coastal Resilience Africa (CityCORE). \$980,000 02/2018 - 08/2019

VIII) Strengthening Global Hydromet System - Investment Support. \$1,400,000 08/2015 - 07/2019

IX) Strengthening DRR Coordination, Planning and Policy Advisory Capacity of ECOW-AS, \$1,977,500 06/2015 - 12/2019

X) Strengthening DRR Coordination, Planning and Policy Advisory Capacity of ECOWAS. \$1,285,000 10/2016 - 06/2019

4.2.2 *The UNDP* – The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) that operates in 177 countries and territories of the world, is the UN’s global development network that partners with people at all levels of society to help build nations that can withstand crisis, and sustain the kind of growth that improves the quality of life for everyone. In Nigeria of recent, UNDP and Japan supports IDPs in North East of Nigeria. With funding from the Government of Japan, UNDP and its implementing partners continues to provide support to people affected by the ongoing military insurgency in North East region of Nigeria. This support is being channelled through two projects; one focusing on Livelihood and Social Cohesion, while the other on De-radicalization, Counter-Terrorism and Migration.

Also, the pupils of Ngwom Primary School in the North East Nigeria were glad to be back after their school were destroyed in 2016 crisis. Collective learning in classrooms environment were restored through the assistance of the Japan Government, the EU government, Swiss government and the Borno State Government that rebuilt and furnished 12 classrooms, offices, stores, and toilets.

In the areas of capacity development, UNDP has been supporting NEMA in series of national programmes on DRR like the Risk Identification, Monitoring and Assessment (**RIMA, 2018-2020**). NEMA needs to develop appropriate capacity for undertaking risk identification, monitoring and assessment so as to provide logical steps and actions required for an efficient and effective disaster risk management at different levels in the country. Specifically, RIMA products for stakeholders’ consumption are:

- a) transformation and strengthening of the GIS Unit of NEMA
- b) development of a national training programme in RIMA for SEMAs, MDAs and other stakeholders;
- c) identification of support roles for CSDDRR: (i) training and partnering SEMAs to undertake their programmes; (ii) undertaking RIMA activities as consultancies.

4. COVID-19 and Territorial Influence Diplomacy on Nigeria

Sequel to the outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic in mainland China and other countries worldwide, the Federal Government of Nigeria on 31 January set up a Coronavirus Preparedness Group so as to mitigate the impact of the virus if it eventually spreads to the country (Ifijeh 2020, MSN, 2020). Coincidentally, the World Health Organization (WHO) on the same day, listed Nigeria among other 13 African countries identified as high-risk for the spread of the virus (Ezigbo and Ifijeh, 2020). The first index case was confirmed in the country on 27 February and was transferred to Lagos State biosecurity facilities for isolation and testing, (Gesinde 2020), Ugbodaga 2020). Consequently, as of August, 2020, 48,116 cases have been confirmed, 34,309 cases have been treated and discharged, while 966 deaths have been recorded in 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory, (NCDC, 2020)

The Bill for an Act to establish Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) was signed into law in November 2018, by President Muhammadu Buhari. The mission for the NCDC (2017-2021) is ‘To protect the health of Nigerians through evidence-based prevention, integrated disease surveillance and response activities, using a one health approach, guided by research and led by a skilled workforce’ The post economic impact of COVID-19 is expected to be severe because, even before the pandemic outbreak, Nigeria’s economy was already

nose-diving following the falling of per capita GDP levels and the sharp fall in oil prices which magnified the vulnerabilities level and historic decline in growth and large financing needs. These shocks have created large external and financing needs for 2020. Additional declines in oil prices and more protracted containment measures would seriously affect the real and financial sectors and strain the country's financing.

The concept of collective responsibility in fighting COVID-19 advocated by WHO has played out for a country like Nigeria who hitherto lack the required manpower, health infrastructure, and political will ion curtailing the adverse impact of the pandemic as envisaged. Zhang and Dolan (2020) in their work on China-US COVID-19 disaster diplomacy quoting Lee and Smith (2011) define global health diplomacy as "policy shaping processes through which state, non-state and other institutional actors negotiate responses to health challenges, or utilize health concepts or mechanisms in policy-shaping and negotiation strategies, to achieve other political, economic or social objectives." The two contesting economic world power (China and US) have been playing superior donor 'fatherism' to developing countries most especially on Nigeria because of their market economy. In fact, while countries like US are talking of when and how to sell the COVID-19 vaccine developing countries like Nigeria, China has promised to assist Nigeria with the same vaccine soonest.

Academia's like Colglazier (2020) and Qingguo (2020) has argued that despite America's strong links between science, policy and society, they has failed to capitalize on this knowledge when it is most needed. While: China's diplomacy is fending off Western attacks and endorsing international efforts to fight the pandemic. .Table 1 shows the external aids given to the country in combating the pandemic, and this has drastically reduced the death rate to about 966 as of august, 2020 in a country of over 200 million population with high poverty rate.

Table 1. Foreign Aids to Nigeria on COVID-19

S/N	Country/Organization	Amount (\$)
1	IMF	3.4bilion
2	USA (USAID)	32.8 million
3	China	48 million
4	UKAid	£661,000
5	Africa Dev. Bank	\$288.5 million

Generally, Nigeria as a nation has benefited from international collaboration with government agencies and NGOs in building her disaster resilience to the community levels Nigeria is a major market for manufactured goods across the world, hence the rate of grants, loans and aids to the country.

5.1 Discussion - Foreign aid and International Coalition for Disaster Management

Foreign aid in the works of Chung et al (2020) citing authors like (Bueno de Mesquita and Smith, 2009; Kuziemko and Werker, 2006; and Woo and Chung, 2018) is a tool with which donors manoeuvre policies and opinions of its recipients UN General Assemblies or winkle out policy concessions from recipients. Awareness of donor competition often boost support for aid where donors seeks for national pride, humanitarian value, and instrumental value of foreign aid. Although the global pandemic has local implications, yet local mismanage-

ment of the disease has colossal international implications as can be inferred from Wuhan in China. This has necessitated the scholarly comparison of countries' geo-administration, different policy levels updates, and public health outcomes over time and cross nationally. Professionals in sociology have seen disaster (especially COVID-19) as laboratory for the study of sociology of disaster as it serve as avenue to test many hypothesis like the theory of Disaster Diplomacy. Developing countries like Nigeria have benefited immensely in both cash and kind from the global pandemic through international collaboration coupled with humanitarian pride that promotes willingness to aid out-groups due to the fact that collective pride is generally a positive emotion as is being demonstrated by China in the management of COVID-19.

In disaster information disseminations, the reception and interpretation of the information content is a function of the existing levels of socioeconomic inequality. The flow of information to and from citizens and policy makers coated with emotional words convey meanings outside cultural and textual context and can serve as an important measure of emotional effects of natural or human-induced disasters, that is critical to successful management and preservation of public health. Foreign aids without direct citizen welfare distort information flow and assimilation and this is the bane of the poor disaster resilient level in most African countries.

Conclusion

Disasters occurrences globally seem to be on the increase due the growth in the reporting system that is space and information technology based (CNN, Aljazeera, VOA, etc). This paper examines the role of collaboration and foreign aids in managing natural disasters and in particular the global pandemic COVID-19, the management of natural disaster and the COVID-19 by Nigeria government with the intervention of international donor agencies of which researchers like Chung et al (2020), and Ferry and Cleo (2020) admitted to have some political undertone and territorial influences. It also addresses the issue of China-US competition in global economic power struggle as it affect aids to developing countries like Nigeria. All hese then serve as laboratory for both sociologist and researchers in international relations in the analysis of disaster aid diplomacy as already observed by Ferry and Cleo (2020) and DHS (2009). The pattern and levels of cities development shapes disaster risk, and disaster risk also shapes development possibilities since human life itself is risk as they are causers of risk and recipients of risk.

Since disaster is not territorial boundary bound, there should be vertical and horizontal cooperation between and within nations of the world in the area of community awareness, prevention, preparedness, and mitigation of disaster. Risk pulling is one of the best practices that should be imbibed by every nation and communities. Going by the official definition of disaster or catastrophe, the challenging phenomena or episode must be beyond the coping capacity of the affected nation, region or community, thereby requiring external intervention. Countries therefore needs symbiotic partnership through international treaties in build a formidable resilient nation.

Recommendations

Disaster has been generally accepted as every man's business and the world as a global village in which local mismanagement of environmental disaster often boomeranged to the global level (Wuham-China) calls for the following recommendations:

I) Nations and regions having the same environmental challenges establish more treaties that are not based on tokenism. This is very apparent in the way banditry and Boko-Haram is being handled between Nigeria and the neighbouring countries.

II) International bodies though having different aim and objectives should harmonize their responses in affected communities to avoid unintended humanitarian environmental impacts.

III) International organizations and NGOs should direct more of their assistance toward building early warning systems and human capacity in the developing countries. These will help to reduce the colossal amount of dollars wasted in relief packages that is never enough.

IV) The international court of justice should be more proactive in intervening in governments that perpetrates injustice before it degenerated into genocide as in Somali, Rwanda-Burundi.

V) Federal government agencies should incorporate national resilience as a guiding principle to inform the mission and actions of the federal government and the programs it supports at all levels.

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